

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

JOURNAL OF TERTIARY AND INDUSTRIAL SCIENCES

A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF THE HIGHER TECHNICAL TEACHERS'
TRAINING COLLEGE, KUMBA

VOLUME 5, NUMBER 1
FEBRUARY, 2025

PUBLISHER:
HIGHER TECHNICAL TEACHERS' TRAINING COLLEGE (HTTC)
UNIVERSITY OF BUEA

P.O Box: 249 Buea Road, Kumba
Tel: (+237) 33354691 – Fax: (+237) 33354692
Email: editor@jtis-htttcubuea.com
Website: <https://www.jtis-htttcubuea.com>

EDITORIAL BOARD

Supervision:

Professor Ngomo Horace Manga
University of Buea

Editor-in-Chief:

Prof. Akume Daniel Akume, University of Buea, Cameroon

Associate Editors:

Prof. Ebune B. Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Defang Henry, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Lissouck Daniel, University of Buea, Cameroon

Advisory Editors:

Prof. Tabi Johannes Atemnkeng, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Leno Doris, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Lyonga N. Agnes Ngale, University of Buea, Cameroon

Members of the Editorial Board:

Prof. Yamb Belle Emmanuel, University of Douala, Cameroon

Prof. Ambe Njoh Jonathan, University of South Florida, USA

Prof. John Akande, Bowen University, Nigeria

Prof. Talla Pierre Kisito, University of Dschang, Cameroon

Prof. Rosemary Shafack, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Njimanted Godfrey Forgha, University of Bamenda, Cameroon

Prof. Nzalie Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Mouange Ruben, IUT University of Ngaoundere, Cameroon

Prof. Boum Alexander, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Patrick Wanyu Kongnyuy, University of Bamenda, Cameroon

Prof. Tchuen Ghyslain, IUT Badjoun, University of Dschang, Cameroon

Prof. Rose Frii-Manyi Anjoh, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Foadieng Emmanuel, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Tchinda Rene, IUT Badjoun, University of Dschang, Cameroon

Prof. Tabi Pascal Tabot, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Katte Valentine, University of Bamenda, Cameroon

Prof. Zinkeng Martina, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Obama Belinga Christian Theophile, University of Ebolowa, Cameroon

Prof. Nkongho Anyi Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Cordelia Givechek Kometa, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Ngouateu Wouagfack Paiguy, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Tchakoutio Alain, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Morfaw Bertrand, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Tamba Gaston, IUT University, Douala, Cameroon
Prof. Koumi Simon, ENS, Ebolowa, University of Yaounde I
Prof. Ajongakoh Raymond, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Ntabe Eric, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Kinfack Juetsa Aubin, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Bahel Benjamin, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Agbortoko Ayuk Nkem, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Abanda Henry Fonbiyen, Oxford Brookes University, UK
Dr. Luis Alberto Torrez Cruz, University of Witwatersrand, South Africa
Dr. Negou Ernest, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Aloyem Kaze Claude Vidal, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Mfombep Priscilla Mebong, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Asoba Gillian, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Massa Ernest, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Mouzong Pemi, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Orock Fidelis Tanyi, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Wanie Clarkson Mvo, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Dr. Molombe Jeff Mbella, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Emmanuel Tata Sunjo, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Ndi Roland Akoh, University of Yaounde I, Cameroon
Dr. Nkenganyi Fonkem Marcellus, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Hannah Kolle, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Kamda Silapeux Aristide, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Roland Ndah Njoh, University of Buea, Cameroon

Managing Editor:

Dr. Negou Ernest, University of Buea, Cameroon

Effects of soil pH and moisture content on morphology, biomass traits and leaf chlorophyll content of <i>Voacanga africana</i> Stapf.....	1
Working Capital Management Practices and Lending Decisions in Microfinance Institutions. The Case of Buea Municipality in Cameroon.....	11
Human Resource Audit and Engagement of Employees in SMES in Yaounde, Cameroon	40
Structural Change from Agriculture to Industry on Environmental Degradation in Sub-Saharan Africa	62
Child Trafficking in Conflicts: An Appraisal of Cameroon’s Legal Framework	82

Child Trafficking in Conflicts: An Appraisal of Cameroon's Legal Framework

¹ Ndinge Nadia Mbella Ph.D

² Mojoko Fiona Mbella Ph.D

Part-time Lecturer, Dept. of English Law, Faculty of Laws & Political Science, University of Buea, Cameroon. ndingenadia@gmail.com

Lecturer, Dept. of Geography, Faculty of Social & Management Sciences, University of Buea, Cameroon. mojoko.fiona@ubuea.cm

Submission Date: 25/11/2024

Acceptation Date: 20/01/2025

Abstract

Child trafficking is a grave violation of children's fundamental human rights and dignity. While the phenomenon has existed in Cameroon for years, the Boko Haram insurgency and the ongoing conflict in the two English-speaking regions have significantly heightened children's vulnerability to trafficking, as they are easily manipulated and exploited than adults. This paper critically examines Cameroon's legal framework on child trafficking in conflict situations. It employs the qualitative research methodology and makes use of the doctrinal method of content analysis. The paper is grounded on Henry Shue's Triple-Pronged theory which outlines states obligations to respect, protect, and fulfill basic human rights of all citizens. Findings reveal that Cameroon has ratified and enacted several anti-trafficking laws. However, vague and inconsistent language in key legal instruments hinders effective implementation. To address these shortcomings, this paper recommends a comprehensive review of anti-trafficking laws to align with contemporary trends and international best practices.

Keywords: Child, Child Trafficking, Conflict, Legal Framework

1. Introduction

Child trafficking flourishes during conflicts, where instability increases children's exposure to exploitation. Conflict influence the form and the severity of trafficking-related exploitation.¹ This phenomenon is contrary to basic human rights principles and violates the essentials of international humanitarian law applicable in times of war. The Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) 1989, defines a child as persons below the age of 18 years, affirming their entitlement to special care and protection during both peacetimes and armed conflicts. The international humanitarian law (IHL) distinguishes between two types of armed conflicts; those of an international character (cross-border

¹ J. Muraszkiwicz et al, 'Human Trafficking in Conflict: Context, Causes and the military, Crime Prevention and Security Management', *International Journal of Refugee Law*, Vol 33, Issue 2, 2021, pp 368-371.

conflicts) and those of a non-international character (internal conflicts). According to **Common Article 3** of the 1949 Geneva Conventions, internal conflicts are those that take place within the territory of one of the High Contracting Parties. This may involve two or more non-governmental armed groups fighting each other or a conflict between a governmental and a non-governmental armed group. For a conflict to be classified as a non-international armed conflict, certain factors are taken into consideration:

- The hostilities must reach a certain level of intensity, be of a collective nature, and necessitate the use of military force rather than mere police intervention.
- The non-governmental armed group must be recognised as a 'party to the conflict', meaning it must demonstrate a certain level of organisation and a command structure capable of sustaining military operations.

The ongoing Boko Haram insurgency and the conflict in the two English-speaking regions of Cameroon constitute non-international armed conflict in line with **Common Article 3** of the Geneva Conventions (1949).²

The term 'trafficking' broadly applies to various practices; forced migration, facilitated migration, the exploitation of prostitution, to the movement of persons through the threat or use of force, coercion, violence for certain exploitative purposes.³ According to the United Nations Protocol to Prevent, Suppress, and Punish Trafficking in Persons (Palermo Protocol, 2000), child trafficking is the recruitment, transfer, harbouring and receipt of persons below the age of 18 years for exploitation. The consent of the child is always irrelevant. Traffickers exploit children for various purposes, including unlawful recruitment and use of child soldiers, forced labour, sexual exploitation, domestic servitude, organ harvesting and ritual sacrifices, among others.⁴ This exploitation severely harms their physical, psychological, emotional and moral development, thereby depriving them of all their fundamental rights guaranteed under the CRC.⁵

The United Nations Security Council identifies three primary forms of trafficking in conflicts;⁶

² L. Nagavveni, 'International and Non-International Armed Conflicts and Application of International Humanitarian Law as *Lex Specialis*', *Chotangpur Law Journal*, Vol 11, No. 11, 2017, p.78-91

³ M. Dempsey, et al 'Defining Sex Trafficking in International and Domestic Law: Mind the Gaps', *Emory International Law Review*, 2012, Vol 26 pp. 136-162

⁴ P. Hughues, Child's Right Protection in Cameroon, *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, ISSN NO: 2769-996X 2024 P. 5

⁵ N. Mbella, Human Rights Implications of Child Trafficking in Conflict Situations: Case Study of the Conflict in the English Speaking Region of Cameroon, *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2021 pp

⁶Global Initiative Against Transnational Organised Crime, *Connecting Human Trafficking and Conflict*, available at globalinitiative.net last accessed 15th July, 2024.

- Trafficking within conflict-affected areas (involves trafficking children within the confines of those areas and also displacing them from other safe areas into the conflict areas).
- Recruitment by non-state armed groups (here, children are forcibly conscripted as combatants, spies, suicide bombers or servants).
- Trafficking from conflict zones to external regions (trafficking of children out of and through conflict zones to supposedly safer regions for exploitation).

Under international human rights law, states have the responsibility to respect, protect and fulfill fundamental rights in both peacetimes and during conflicts. The Triple-Pronged theory provides a framework for evaluating state responsibility in combatting child trafficking. In this regard, it is commendable that Cameroon is a State Party to several international human rights and anti-trafficking conventions, indicating its firm willingness to curb the ill. The anti-trafficking regulatory frameworks directly address trafficking, related activities and other societal issues that contribute to the problem. Despite the existence of these laws, ongoing conflicts and inconsistencies within legal frameworks continue to undermine their effectiveness.

2. Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

Child trafficking in conflict has taken its toll in the world with grave ramifications on victims, families, communities and nations as a whole. The lives of children destroyed as a result of this, has raised global concerns and an upsurge of interest in researchers to extensively examine the causes, consequences and legal responses. This section reviews key literature relevant to child trafficking in conflict situations, highlighting gaps and limitations in existing studies.

Deshpande and Nawal⁷ argue that women and adolescent girls are the primary victims of trafficking, particularly sex trafficking, which leads to physical and psychological harm. While their study provides important gender-based insights, it is limited in scope as it overlooks other forms of child trafficking, such as the use of child soldiers, forced labour, organ harvesting and ritual killings which are common in conflicts. This study builds on their work by broadening the focus on various dimensions of child trafficking in conflict areas.

Nji Lilian⁸ examines the effectiveness of international conventions in combatting child labour in conflicts, arguing that child labour deprives children of education and

⁷ N. Deshpande and N. Nawal, 'Sex Trafficking of women and girls', National Centre for Biotechnology information, Rockville Pike, 2013, issue PMC3651545 PP. 22-27

⁸ L. Nji, 'The Enforceability of International conventions Against child labour in Cameroon: Implications for Human Security in Armed Conflicts in the North West and South West Regions, Published PhD Thesis on Comparative Politics, 2021

endangers their well-being. While she acknowledges the progress made through international legal instruments, she also highlights cultural challenges that hinder enforcement. Unlike child labour, child trafficking is broader in scope, involving coercion, deception and exploitation for multiple purposes. This includes the unlawful recruitment and use of child soldiers, sexual exploitation, debt bondage, rituals and organ harvesting. This paper differs from the author's work by examining legal loopholes that weaken Cameroon's anti-trafficking efforts and identifies gaps in existing mechanisms.

Beatrice Titanji⁹ explores the role of civil society organisations in combatting trafficking in persons in Cameroon. She argues that civil society organisations are crucial in the fight against trafficking in persons through sensitisation campaigns and the empowerment of impoverished families. However, while civil societies play a crucial role in raising awareness, state actions remain the primary determinant of success in the fight against TIP. This study shifts the focus to state responsibility, highlighting Cameroon's legal obligations and assessing the gaps in the country's anti-trafficking laws.

This paper is underpinned by the Triple-Pronged theory formulated by Henry Shue. The theory outlines state's tripartite duty to respect, to protect and fulfill the basic human rights of its citizens. The duty to respect means that states should refrain from violating the human rights of citizens. The duty to protect explains states should ensure other persons (individuals, corporations, non-state actors), do not infringe on the rights of citizens while the duty to fulfill charges states to take all positive measures to ensure they meet the needs of their citizens.

In relation to child trafficking, the duty to respect ensures that states do not directly engage, support or facilitate trafficking activities. In conflict areas, governments must not recruit child soldiers or exploit children for exploitative purposes. The duty to protect urges states to safeguard children from being trafficked through the creation of robust legal frameworks to criminalise the act and prosecute perpetrators who violate these laws. Moreover, the duty to fulfill ensures states must take active measures to provide support systems for vulnerable children, including rehabilitation centres and educational programs. Cameroon has made significant strides towards curbing the ill of child trafficking through the ratification and enactment of legislation.

3. Research Methodology

The study employs the qualitative research methodology, which analyses non-numerical data. It adopts the doctrinal method of research, involving a content analysis of existing literature. The primary sources of data collection include reviewing treaties and

⁹ B. Titanji, 'Curbing the Tides of Human Trafficking and Slavery', Design House Publishers, Limbe, Cameroon, 2019

legislation while secondary sources involve the use of textbooks, articles and websites. This approach is suitable as it provides a deeper understanding of the concept of child trafficking in conflicts as outlined in legal instruments.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 International Laws

The aftermath of World War II heightened global awareness of human rights protection, leading to the adoption of numerous international conventions to combat trafficking in persons, particularly child trafficking. Cameroon as a State Party to several international treaties, has incorporated some of these obligations into its domestic legal framework. Under **Article 45** of the Constitution of Cameroon, all duly ratified international laws take precedence over national laws.

4.1.1 The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) 1948

The historic declaration commonly referred to as UDHR, was proclaimed by the United Nations General Assembly in Paris on 10th December, 1948 as ‘a common human rights standard of achievement for all peoples and nations.’¹⁰ It sets out the basic civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights that people ought to enjoy.¹¹ The UDHR is pivotal in protecting human rights as it sets the expected standards to be adopted by nations.¹² It serves as the foundation upon which other human rights treaties stems. It emphasises that ‘all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights’ and none shall be discriminated upon, based on race, sex, language or religion.¹³ It was triggered by the millions of men, women and children who were enslaved in the most brutal forms of forced labour, sexual servitude and other forms of exploitation during the Second World War, serving as a haunting backdrop for the adoption of **Article 4**.¹⁴ This article prohibits slavery or servitude, aligning with modern anti-trafficking laws. The UDHR contains two provisions specifically addressing children’s rights. **Article 25(2)**, guarantees special care and assistance for children, regardless of their birth circumstances (whether born in or out of wedlock) while **Article 26**, establishes the right to free and compulsory elementary education, reinforcing the need to combat trafficking, which often deprives children of schooling. Education is directed towards the full development of the human personality. Thus, crimes like trafficking which keeps children away from school is strongly condemned.

Although the UDHR is not legally binding on states, it serves as evidence of their shared commitment to prohibiting slavery in all its forms. It has acquired the status of *jus cogens*

¹⁰ Adopted on December 10, 1948, GA Resolution 217 (III) United Nations Doc A/810, 1994

¹¹ UDHR Preamble

¹² J. Sloth–Nielsen, ‘A Dutiful Child: The Implications of Article 31 of the African Children’s Charter’, *Journal of African Law* 2008, Vol 52, No 2, 159-189, 159

¹³ Article 1 of the UDHR, 1948

¹⁴ M. Sands, UDHR and Modern Slavery: Exploring the Challenges of Fulfilling the Universal Promise to End Slavery in All its Forms, *The Political Quarterly*

and has therefore become part of customary international law which binds states. *Jus cogens* are fundamental principles of international law that are recognised as being of universal importance and are non-derogable. Many of the provisions of the UDHR have been incorporated into legally binding treaties, such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant of Economic, Social and Cultural rights, 1966. The prohibition of slavery has been codified through multiple international treaties today and have been enshrined in the preamble of the Constitution of Cameroon.

4.1.2 The Geneva Conventions of 1949 and their Additional Protocols

International humanitarian law (IHL) is based on the principles of humanity, impartiality and neutrality, providing protection to a wide range of persons and objects during armed conflicts. Adopted on August 12, 1949 and universally ratified, the Geneva Conventions and their Additional Protocols protect the sick, wounded and shipwrecked individuals not taking part in hostilities, prisoners of war and other detainees, civilians and civilian objects.¹⁵ It explicitly prohibits the use of child soldiers, stating that 'children must not be recruited into armed forces and must not be allowed to participate in hostilities. Thus, the recruitment of child soldiers by boko haram and the ambazonian non-state armed groups is strongly condemned.

4.1.2.1 Geneva Convention IV Relating to the Protection of Civilians in Times of War 1949

It was ratified by Cameroon in 1963. The IV Geneva Convention obligates states to protect civilians and civilian property in times of war. The major principle of IHL that ensures the protection of civilians is the fundamental distinction between civilian population and combatants, as well as between civilian objects and military objects. The civilian population includes people who are not or are no longer taking part in hostilities (*hors de combat*). **Article 24** of the convention mandates that parties to the conflict take all necessary measures to ensure that children under 15 years old who are orphaned or are separated from their families as a result of war, are not left to fend for themselves. Instead these children should receive proper care, including shelter, food, and medical attention. This is a preventive action in curbing child trafficking as it ensures separated and unaccompanied children protected to reduce their vulnerability. **Article 51(2)**, of the 1949 Geneva Convention IV provides that the occupying power may not compel or enlist children to serve in its armed or auxiliary forces unless they are over 18 years. This therefore means the recruitment of child soldiers by warring parties is forbidden at all times.

¹⁵ Protected Persons, www.icrc.org>war-and-law last accessed 10th March, 2021.

4.1.2.2 Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions and Relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts 1977

It was adopted on the 8th of June, 1977 and was ratified by Cameroon in 1984. Participation of children in armed hostilities occurs too frequently and in diverse ways. This participation may range from aiding combatants (children sent to bring their weapons), to the actual recruitment of children as combatants. **Article 77(2)** of the 1977 Additional Protocol I, provides: the parties to the conflict shall take feasible measures in order that children who have not attained the age of 15 years do not take direct part in hostilities and, in particular, they shall refrain from recruiting them into their armed forces.

4.1.2.3 Additional Protocol II to the Geneva Conventions Relating to the Protection of Victims in Non-International Armed Conflicts 1977

This Protocol was adopted on the 8th of June, 1977 and ratified by Cameroon in 1984. **Article 4** states that children require special care and protection. It also explicitly prohibits slavery in all its forms. Furthermore, the protocol condemns both recruitment and the direct or indirect participation of children under 15 years in hostilities. This provision specifically prohibits the use of children as soldiers, spies, suicide bombers, and cooks, as these are common forms of trafficking during armed conflicts.

4.1.3 The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) (1966)¹⁶

The UDHR, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), and the International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) are collectively considered the Bill of Rights under international law. These documents establish the legal basis for children's rights worldwide. The ICCPR and the ICESCR were initially adopted by the United Nations on the 16th of December 1966, entered into force on the 3rd of January 1976 and ratified by Cameroon in 1984. **Article 2** of the ICCPR advocated for non-discrimination and ensures States must respect all covenant rights of individuals within their territory and jurisdiction. **Article 6** of the ICCPR recognises an individual's 'inherent right to life' and requires that it be protected by law. The Covenant also condemns slavery and forced labour in **Article 8**, while **Article 9** upholds the right to liberty and security of persons, which is often violated when children are trafficked. To safeguard these rights, states are obliged to prevent and combat child trafficking. **Article 21(2)** affords protection to all children without discrimination on the grounds of race, color, religion, social origin or birth. **Article 23(3)** outlaws forced marriages which is a prevalent form of child trafficking in conflict as a means of survival. **Article 24** recognises that children need enhanced protection and therefore urges states to put special protective measures conducive to the enjoyment of human rights of all children.

¹⁶ A6316 (Dec 16, 1966), International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. G. A Res.2200A(XXI), UN. GAOR, 21st sess. supp. No. 16, at 52,999. U.N.T.S. 171 (entered into force 23rd March, 1976)

Following these provisions, the state has obligation to uphold the principles of equality and non-discrimination.

4.1.4 The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) (1966)¹⁷

It was adopted on the 16th of December, 1966 by the UN General Assembly and it came into force on the 3rd of January 1976. **Article 2(2)** of the ICESCR emphasises non-discrimination in the enjoyment of economic, social and cultural rights. Women are given protection under this provision as they are often discriminated against due to their vulnerability. The ICESCR addresses the underlying causes of trafficking as it obliges states to provide housing needs, education, proper health services and employment opportunities to persons in its **Articles 11, 12, 13, and 14**. This goes a long way to reduce the number of impoverished children exposed to trafficking. Moreover, states have the duty to prohibit and punish acts engaging women (girls) in hazardous work which exposes them to risks as outlined in **Article 10**.

4.1.5 The Protocol to Prevent, Suppress, and Punish Trafficking in Persons (TIP) Especially Women and Children (Palermo Protocol) (2000)

The Protocol was adopted by the UN General Assembly in 2000 and entered into force on Dec 25th, 2003 to supplement the United Nations Convention on Transnational Organised Crime and Drugs. It was ratified by Cameroon on the 18th of November, 2004. This law clearly links the crime of child trafficking to international organised crime. The Palermo Protocol defines an organised criminal group as "a structured group of three or more persons existing for a period of time, having the aim of committing a serious crime in order to, directly or indirectly, obtain a financial or other material benefit." The Palermo Protocol provided the first ever comprehensive definition of trafficking in persons and lays out the parameters for who constitutes a victim.¹⁸ It serves as a benchmark for states to take joint actions towards the fight against trafficking as a transnational crime. **Article 2** obliges states to prevent and combat TIP, protect and assist victims, and promote cooperation among states in the fight. ¹⁹

The Palermo Protocol looks at trafficking from both a criminal justice and a human rights perspective. The protocol criminalises TIP, requiring states to adopt laws that punish perpetrators while the human rights perspective emphasises the protection of victims. Summarily, this is considered the 3(P) approach towards combatting trafficking in

¹⁷ A6316 (Dec 16, 1966), International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural rights. G.A Res.2200A(XXI),UN.GAOR, 21st sess,supp. No. 16, at 49,993.U.N.T.S.3 (entered into force 3rd January 1976)

¹⁸ R. Vijayarasa, A move in the Right Direction? The Model Law against Trafficking in Persons and the ILO Operational Indicators, International Migration 2018, Vol.57 Issue 1, 177-191

¹⁹ Article 2 of the UN Palermo Protocol 2000

persons; **prevention, protection and prosecution**.²⁰ Prevention deals with addressing the root causes of trafficking through awareness campaigns, poverty reduction strategies and improving socio-economic conditions that reduce vulnerabilities. Protection deals with safeguarding the rights and well-being of trafficked victims while prosecution aims at holding traffickers accountable. **Article 5** encourages measures to discourage factors that foster trafficking. The three P approach has subsequently been complemented with the 3(R) approach which stands for **Rescue, Rehabilitation and Reintegration** of victims. However, the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, 1998 which gives backing to the Palermo Protocol has not been ratified by Cameroon as this further impedes on the implementation of the law in Cameroon.

Another weakness of the Palermo Protocol is that it relies on national governments for implementation, with no direct enforcement by the United Nations. Moreover, while the protocol defines trafficking, terms like 'exploitation' are broad, leading to inconsistent interpretation and application among countries.

4.1.6 The Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989)

The Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) was adopted by the UN in 1989 and entered into force in 1990. The CRC was the first international treaty to address specifically the legal rights of children. It is the most universally accepted human rights treaty and was ratified by Cameroon on 11th January, 1993.²¹ The CRC defines who a child is, their rights and the responsibilities of states towards the protection and promotion of these rights. It brought forth the principle of "**the best interest of the child**", and for the first time gave voice to children in that ways must be found to ensure that children are able to participate in matters affecting them.²² It expressly states that in all actions undertaken by states, institutions and private entities, the best interest of a child must be considered before taking any decision that concerns them. The CRC provides a rights framework for children both in times of peace and times of war.

The adoption of the CRC in the 1980s was at a time when large numbers of children worldwide were not receiving basic human rights.²³ Children deprived of their liberty often lacked legal representation and were subjected to sexual abuse. The legislative history of the CRC clearly demonstrates that it was adopted largely because children were recognised as a particularly vulnerable group, susceptible to various forms of

²⁰ Human Rights Advocates, "Achieving Millennium Development Goals through a Rights-Based Approach for combatting Human trafficking" (<http://www.humanrightsadvocates.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/03/CSW-58-combattingtrafficking.pdf> retrieved 1st April, 2018).

²¹ Convention on the Rights of the Child, New York, 20 November 1989, <https://treaties.un.org> last accessed 9th September, 2024

²² Art. 3 of the CRC 1989

²³ Mower G. A., *The Convention on the Rights of the Child: International Law Support for Children*, 1997, pp. vii, 28 and 41-42. 89

exploitation and abuse. The drafters were deeply concerned about the conditions in which children lived and worked globally. It not only addresses the granting and implementation of rights in peacetime, but also the proper treatment of children in situations of armed conflict. The CRC is primarily concerned with four aspects of children's rights ("the four 'P's"): participation by children in decisions affecting them; protection of children against discrimination and all forms of neglect and exploitation; prevention of harm; and provision of assistance to children for their basic needs. The CRC stipulates that states should protect children from all forms of abuse and many of the articles are of direct relevance regarding child trafficking. **Article 6** specifically guarantees the right to life, survival and development and respect for the views of children in decisions which affect them.

Article 19 (1) and (2) specifically addresses the responsibilities of state parties to protect children from various forms of harm. States are required to adopt appropriate national legislation that aims to protect children from any form of abuse or neglect. Parents and guardians of children equally have a responsibility of safeguarding children's rights and to ensure they are not maltreated.

Article 32 acknowledges the vulnerability of children to economic exploitation and child labour. It urges states to protect children from economic exploitation and from performing any work that is likely to interfere with the child's education, or be harmful to their health, physical, mental, spiritual, moral or social development. Moreover, **Article 35** specifically stipulates that states are obliged to protect children from trafficking: 'States Parties shall take all appropriate national, bilateral and multilateral measures to prevent the abduction of, the sale of or traffic in children for any purpose or in any form'. The CRC holds that children shall not be subjected to torture or other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment (**Article 37**). Moreover, **Article 39** of the CRC, enjoins States to take actions to support the physical and psychological recovery and re-integration of children who were victims of exploitation and abuse. It emphasises the need for comprehensive measures to help these children recover and reintegrate into the society.

The CRC however uses a weak language in its definition of who constitutes a child. For the purposes of the Convention, a child is a person below the age of 18 years unless, under the law applicable majority is attained earlier. This creates a legal loophole, as each state could potentially lower the age of adulthood and reduce protections for children especially, when it comes to issues like marriage, labour or criminal responsibility. In Cameroon, the legal age of marriage is 15 for girls (with parental consent). This falls below the CRC's standard and has been a call for concern. Cameroon also allows children as young as 14 years to start engaging in employment. This is in contrast with international standards set by the International Labour Organisations (ILO), which

generally prohibits child labour. The minimum age of employment in the ILO is 15 years and exceptional 16 in some circumstances. These discrepancies create confusion in uniformly implementing international laws designed to protect children. The CRC envisions a universal understanding of a child as someone under 18, but when national laws diverge, enforcement and adherence to international norms become problematic.

4.1.7 Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the Involvement of Children in Armed Conflicts 2000

This is the main international legal instrument that specifically addresses the use of children as soldiers, the minimum age for compulsory recruitment, voluntary recruitment, and direct participation in hostilities. It was adopted by the GA Resolution A/RES/54/263 of 25 May, 2000 and came into force on 12 February, 2002. Cameroon ratified this treaty in February, 2013. It aims at protecting children in armed conflict, prohibiting children from recruitment and use in hostilities. The Children in Armed Conflict Protocol amends the minimum age for recruitment of persons into armed forces, setting it at 18 years. This aims at better protecting children from being recruited as it is believed the CRC's own minimum age of 15 years for voluntary recruitment does not sufficiently protect children. Therefore, the Optional Protocol raised the threshold to 18 years in order to give children enough time to physically and psychologically develop.

Article 3(3) of the protocol obliges States to maintain safeguards in cases of voluntary recruitment of child soldiers by ensuring such recruitment is genuinely voluntary; by requiring informed consent from the individual's parents or legal guardians; by informing recruits of the duties involved in military service; and by requiring reliable proof of age prior to acceptance into military service. The Convention also urges State Parties to 'take all feasible measures to ensure that members of their armed forces who have not attained the age of 18 years do not take a direct part in hostilities as per **Articles 1 & 2**.²⁴

The term "direct participation in hostilities" in the context of treaties relating to the law of armed conflict has been interpreted in the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court as covering "both direct participation in combat and also active participation in military activities linked to combat such as scouting, spying, sabotage, and the use of children as decoys, couriers or at military checkpoints. Although global treaty ratification signifies ideological agreement that persons under fifteen should not bear arms, perpetrate violence, nor wear the uniform of any combative group in any form of political conflict in the world, the reality on ground is woefully far from this ideal. The protocol is not a perfect piece as it fails to clearly define a "child soldier." In November, 2023, the National Disarmament, Demobilisation and Reintegration Committee of Cameroon reported that 1,189 children were registered at the Meri Center, presumed to be

²⁴ Children in Armed Conflict, Article 1

associated with armed groups.²⁵ This underscores the ongoing challenges related to child soldiers in the country.

4.1.8 Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography 2000

It was adopted by the UN on the 25th of May, 2000 and was ratified by Cameroon in 2019.

Article 1 of the Protocol requires parties to protect the rights and interests of child trafficking victims, child prostitution and child pornography. Children performing sexual acts in exchange for (a promise of) something of value (money, objects, shelter, food, drugs) is completely prohibited by this protocol. The consent of the child is completely immaterial and anyone who lures them into such acts is sanctioned.

4.1.9 The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) 1979

The Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination against Women is an international treaty adopted in 1979 by the United Nations General Assembly and was ratified by Cameroon in 1994. It has been described as an international bill of rights for women, which specifically addresses their gender-related concerns. The convention directly addresses and calls for the abolition of all forms of discrimination against women and girls.²⁶ Its adoption stemmed from the realisation that the incorporation of provisions prohibiting sex-based discriminations and affirming the principle of equality in the enjoyment of human rights was not sufficiently addressed by the ICCPR & ICESCR. The majority of trafficking victims identified are females.²⁷ CEDAW therefore makes specific reference to trafficking; identifying it as a form of gender-based violence 'incompatible with the equal enjoyment of rights of women and girls.'²⁸ In order to combat trafficking, the Committee to CEDAW identifies states that serve as countries of origin, transit and destination for victims and has encouraged the punishment of perpetrators on all fronts. It recommends countries to educate public officials, law enforcers, the judiciary and health care providers to fight all forms of violence against females. CEDAW's general recommendations encourages states to address underlying structural gender and socio-economic inequalities that make women and girls more vulnerable in the society. **Article 6** sets out the legal obligations states have in adopting appropriate measures in suppressing all forms of trafficking in women and exploitation of the prostitution of

²⁵ Child soldiers International, Alternative report to the Committee on the Rights of the Child: Cameroon, available at <https://www.refworld.org/reference/country/rep> last retrieved 3rd February, 2025.

²⁶ N. Eyumeneh, 'Breast Ironing, a Silent Case of Violence Against Girls in Cameroon', *Republica y Derecho*, 2023 pp. 1-67

²⁷ General recommendation No. 38 (2020) on trafficking in women and girls in the context of global migration, available at www.reliefweb.int last accessed 10th March, 2024.

²⁸ A Significant Step Forward: CEDAW Committee adopts new General Recommendation on Trafficking in Women and Girls, www.equalitynow.org last accessed 10th March, 2024.

women/girls.²⁹ Despite CEDAW's commitment in fighting trafficking, it is however, limited as deep rooted gender discriminatory practices continue to linger.

4.1.10 The Convention for the Suppression of the Traffic in Persons and of the Exploitation and Prostitution of Others (1949)

The Convention was approved on 2nd December, 1949 and came into effect on 25th July, 1951. It condemns the act of prostitution and the traffic and exploitation of women and girls for such purpose. Cameroon acceded to this treaty on the 19th of February, 1982. It recognises that TIP transgress human dignity and worth, further jeopardizing the welfare of victims, families and their community as a whole. It requires states to punish any person who 'procures, entices or leads others for prostitution even with the consent of the person'. Moreover, **Article 2**, further adds that anyone who runs a brothel or rents out his property for that purpose must be punished. Females are given special protection under this convention as they are more susceptible to prostitution.

4.2. Regional Laws

Although child trafficking is a global phenomenon, the practice is particularly rife in the African continent because of widespread conflicts, poverty and increased vulnerability. This saw the need for specific anti-trafficking frameworks pertaining to African states.

4.2.1 African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR) 1981

The ACHPR is a human rights instrument that is intended to promote and protect human rights and basic freedoms in the African Continent.³⁰ The African Charter is therefore a key instrument in the fight against TIP in Africa. It espouses the rights to life, personal integrity, dignity, liberty and security of persons. The human rights policies of the African Charter are monitored by the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights, which reviews states reports concerning human rights situations and receives complaints for alleged violations.³¹ Cameroon ratified this treaty on Sept 18th, 1989, and the provisions of this Charter have been enshrined in the Constitution.

Article 2 of the Charter states that 'every individual shall be entitled to the enjoyment of the rights and freedoms recognised and guaranteed in the Charter, without distinction of any kind such as race, ethnic group, colour, sex, language, religion, political or any other opinion, national and social origin, fortune, birth or any status'. **Article 4** speaks of the inviolable rights of every human. That is, the right to life and the integrity of his person. Thus advocating for the protection of children from trafficking, which is a threat to their fundamental right to life. **Article 18(3)** calls for the elimination of every discrimination

²⁹ CEDAW Emphasises its Concern Over Trafficking in Women and Girls, available at www.opiniojuris.org last accessed 10th March, 2024.

³⁰ African Charter on Human and People's Rights, available at www.achpr.org last accessed 10th March, 2024.

³¹ Cameroon, <https://www.ijrcenter.org/country-factsheets> last accessed 10th March, 2024.

against women/ girls and ensures the protection of the rights of women and children. It hammers on freedom from slavery and lays emphasis on the security of all persons.

4.2.2 African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child

The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child (ACRWC), is an instrument adopted by the African Union, in July, 1990. The Charter entered into force on 29 November, 1999. The ACRWC was adopted within a year of the adoption of the United Nations CRC. One of the reasons for the separate African Children's Charter was that during the drafting process of CRC, African states were under-represented and as such there was a need for specific provisions to be reiterated from the CRC. In addition, it was considered necessary to address issues pertaining to the African continent, which were not included in the CRC, such as those African practices that have negative effects on the life of girls; displaced persons and the African mindsets on community responsibilities and duties.

The ACRWC, therefore represents a regional effort to protect children in Africa while integrating global human rights concepts. The position of the child in the African society is highlighted by stipulating that the child requires special legal protection as well as "particular care with regard to health, physical, mental, moral and social development." The ACRWC maintains the principles of Non-Discrimination, Best Interests of the child and Survival/Development of the child. It is important because it sets the upper limit of a child's age as per **Article 2**. It states that for purposes of the Charter, a child is every human below the age of 18 years.³² **Article 22** explains that States shall respect and ensure compliance to international humanitarian law applicable in armed conflicts which affects children. They shall take all necessary measures to ensure that no child shall take direct part in hostilities and refrain in particular, from recruiting any child. Furthermore, **Article 29** of this Charter ensures states shall take all appropriate measures to prevent the abduction, the sale of, or trafficking of children for any purpose or in any form, by any form by any person, including parents or legal guardians of the child and the use of children in all forms of begging.

4.2.3 The Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights of Women in Africa (Maputo Protocol).

It became the first and main legal instrument for the protection of women's rights in Africa. The Protocol was adopted by the African Union in July 2003, and entered into force on 25th November, 2005. **Article 14** guarantees women's rights to health. Cameroon ratified the Protocol on 13th September 2012.³³ The Maputo Protocol is premised on the principles of equality between sexes and the elimination of discrimination of women in all spheres of life. **Article 2** calls on states to eliminate harmful cultural practices and all

³² Article 2 of the ACRWC, 1999

³³ www.achpr.org/instruments/ratification last accessed 30th July, 2024

other practices that degrade or discriminate against women, including forced child marriages. Moreover, **Article 4** emphasises the fundamental rights of women and girls, particularly focusing on their right to life, integrity and security. It establishes that states must ensure the protection of these rights.

Although the protocol specifically addresses gender-based violence, its provisions have not been fully implemented in Cameroon due to cultural stereotypes. The Maputo Protocol has not established specific enforcement mechanisms for holding states accountable when they fail to meet their obligations.

4.3 National Laws

Cameroon has enacted several laws to combat child trafficking in conflict situations, both directly and indirectly.

4.3.1 Law No. 96-06 of 18th January 1996 Amending the Constitution of 2nd June 1972 (as Supplemented by Law No. 2008/001 of 14th April 2008)

The Constitution is Cameroon's supreme legal instrument and plays a fundamental role in protecting human rights. Law No. 96-06 of 18th January 1996 amended the Constitution of 2nd June 1972, reinforcing the universal, inherent and inalienable rights of all individuals, regardless of race, religion or sex. The Preamble of the Constitution explicitly upholds the fundamental tenets of equality upheld in the, the UDHR, African Charter and other ratified international treaties. The Preamble to the Constitution is part and parcel of the Constitution as seen in **Article 65** which makes the provisions in the preamble enforceable. Under **Article 45**, duly ratified international laws take precedence over national legislation.³⁴ Therefore, Cameroon's anti-trafficking obligations under international treaties take precedence over national provisions.

4.3.2 The Cameroon Labour Code 1992

The Cameroon Labour Code was instituted by Law No. 92/007 of August 14th 1992 regulates employment relationships and prohibits child labour.³⁵ The law covers a range of issues, including working conditions, wages, labour unions, and employment contracts. Labour Code provides that no Child shall be employed in an enterprise even as an apprentice before the age of 14. **Section 2(1)** defines forced labour as 'any labour or service demanded of an individual under threat of penalty, being a labour or service which the individual has not freely offered to perform.' **Section 2(3)** explicitly prohibits forced or compulsory labour, which aligns with international anti-trafficking frameworks. **Section 86(1)** establishes 14 years as the minimum legal working age, though children below this age may be employed with authorisation from the Minister in Charge of Labour. Furthermore, **Section 82(2)** bans night work, which is prevalent

³⁴ Article 45 of the Constitution of the Republic of Cameroon, 1996

³⁵ Labour Law and Employment Contract in Cameroon, available at www.ngouanalaw.com last accessed 14th March, 2021.

among trafficked children. **Section 87** prohibits children from engaging in perilous work or employment exceeding their physical capabilities.

Despite these provisions, child labour remains prevalent in conflict as children as young as 10 years old are often found hawking goods on the streets of Buea, Kumba, Limbe, Bamenda, Douala, Yaounde, late at night, violating their right to education and exposing them to exploitation.

The implementation of the labour provisions in Cameroon is weak, as child trafficking for forced labour remains prevalent. Children lose their right to decent work and are often compelled to work for long hours without adequate food or proper medical care if they fall ill. Moreover, the provision allowing for the waiver of the minimum age of employment has been criticized as a mere façade.³⁶ The criticism suggests that the government, at its discretion may grant authorization for children under the age of 14 to work, thus enabling child labour. Similarly, setting the minimum age at 14, violates Cameroon's international obligations under the ILO Convention No. 138, which defines children as individuals below 18 and sets the minimum age for work at 15.

4.3.3 The Law Relating to the Fight against Trafficking in Persons and Slavery in Cameroon

Law No. 2011/024 of 14th December 2011, relating to the Fight against Trafficking in Persons and Slavery came in to repeal Law No. 2005/15 of 29th December, 2005 relating to the Fight against Child Trafficking and Slavery. The 2011 anti-trafficking law is divided into three main parts:

Chapter 1 defines key terms, including, trafficking in persons, slavery, debt bondage and exploitation. The law clarifies the fact that victim's consent is irrelevant in cases of trafficking.

Chapter 2 outlines offences and penalties. **Section 3** states that debt bondage shall be punishable by 5-10years imprisonment and a fine of 10,000 FRS to 500,000FCFA. **Section 4** states whoever occasionally engages in the practice of trafficking in persons shall be punished with imprisonment from 10-20years and with a fine from 100,000 to 10,000,000FCFA and **Section 5** states whoever engages in TIP and slavery shall be punished with imprisonment from 15-20years and with a fine from 100,000FCFA to 10,000,000 FCFA where the offence is committed against: a minor of 15years; the perpetrator is a legitimate, natural or adopted ascendant of the victim; the offender has authority over the victim or is expected to participate by virtue of his duties in the fight against slavery or peace keeping; and the offence is committed by an organised gang or association.

³⁶ M. Yanou, *Labour Law: Principles and Practice in Cameroon* (Cameroon: REDEF, 2009, pp. 21-22

Chapter 3 mandates that the law be translated into English and French for public awareness.

Unlike the Palermo Protocol (2000) which applies only to transnational organised crime, Cameroon's law criminalises both domestic and international trafficking.³⁷ Palermo Protocol in **Article 4** outlines when it comes to child trafficking, the Palermo Protocol shall be applicable only where the offences of trafficking are of a transnational nature and done by an organised criminal group. This therefore means it indirectly recognises only international trafficking of children done by an organised criminal group of at least three persons. The 2011 anti-trafficking law recognises that a single perpetrator can be prosecuted for trafficking, even if they are not part of an organised group.

Despite its strength, the 2011 anti-trafficking has significant shortcomings. A thorough evaluation of the law shows that it falls short of achieving its intended goals which are expected to be in line with the Palermo Protocol.³⁸ The 2011 anti-trafficking law does not adhere to the Palermo Protocol's address of TIP, as it fails to incorporate the 'Three P Approach': Prevention, Protection and Prosecution. The 2011 anti-trafficking law focuses predominantly on prosecution while neglecting victim-centered approaches. The 2011 law for instance, lacks mechanisms for victim rehabilitation, reintegration and compensation. No reference is made in the law as regards assisting victims medically and psychologically.

The law fails to differentiate child and adult trafficking. The law treats all trafficking cases the same, ignoring the special needs of child victims.

The law excludes conflict-related trafficking. It does not explicitly address the unlawful recruitment of child soldiers, use of children in terrorism and the trafficking for organ harvesting or ritual killings. Thus, the wordings of the law are considered vague as there are generally provisions against trafficking in persons with no exhaustive reference on all the various manifestations of the phenomenon.

In a nutshell, the law is not comprehensive enough and does not fully observe the minimum criteria set out in the Palermo Protocol. These lacunae pose enormous challenges to the effective implementation of international legal standards against trafficking in persons at the national law.

³⁷ H. Kam, 'Child Trafficking Across the Cameroon/Nigeria Border: A Historical Perspective', *Covenant University Journal of Politics and International Affairs*, Vol. 4 No. 1, pg 1-16, pg 1 2016

³⁸ A. Eyumeneh, 'What does the future hold for our Children? Child Trafficking in Cameroon and India', Published Master's Thesis, Central European University, 2015 p 42

4.3.4 Law No. 2016/007 of July 12, 2016, relating to the Penal Code

Law No. 2016/007 of July 12, 2016, relating to the Penal plays a crucial role in prosecuting trafficking related offences.³⁹ Anti-trafficking laws will not be completely enforced if perpetrators are not punished. **Section 292** and **293** prohibits forced labour and slavery respectively. **Section 292** specifically states that whoever for his personal advantage compels another to do any work or to render any service against his freewill shall be punished with imprisonment from 1 to 5 years or with a fine from 10,000 XAF CFA to 500,000XAF CFA while **Section 293** criminalises slavery with 15-20 years imprisonment. **Section 296** condemns rape with punishment from 5-10years imprisonment. This is helpful since children trafficked are exposed to such dangers. With the penalties given in the Penal Code, people are protected from trafficking since it serves as deterrence to defaulters. Furthermore, **Section 342** of the Penal Code bans slavery and the pawning of minors, with imprisonment from 15-20years. **Section 343** criminalises prostitution and gives imprisonment of 12 months to 10 years and a fine of 20,000 to 1,000,000XAF CFA.

The Penal Code however fails to explicitly prohibit the use of children for illegal activities such as street begging and forced hawking during school hours/late nights- all of which are linked to trafficking. The penal code should be criminalized to include all forms of child exploitation.

4.3.5 Law No. 2014/028 of 23rd December 2014 on the Suppression of Acts of Terrorism (Anti-Terrorism Law)

Law No. 2014/028 of 23rd December, 2014 on the Suppression of Acts of Terrorism.⁴⁰ The anti-terrorism law was introduced to combat Boko Haram insurgency in the northern Cameroon.⁴¹ Undeniably, there is a strong inter-connection between acts of terrorism and trafficking in persons. Terrorist organisations use trafficking as a tool for financing, recruitment, exploitation and control in conflict zones. Through the sale of trafficked persons, terrorists generate revenue to fund their operations. Many terrorist groups forcibly recruit children for combat, intelligence gathering, and suicide bombings. terrorism.⁴² Through the buying and selling of children, terrorists make enough money to sponsor their terrorist activities.

The law punishes 'whoever, acting alone as an accomplice or accessory, commits or threatens to commit an act likely to cause death, endanger physical integrity, cause bodily injury or material damage, destroy natural resources, the environment or cultural heritage, with intent to intimidate the public, provoke a situation of terror, disrupt the

³⁹ Cameroon Penal Code, <https://www.justiceandpeacebamenda.org> last accessed 24th April, 2024

⁴⁰ J. Ashukem, 'To give a dog a bad name to kill It-Cameroon's anti-terrorism law as a strategic framework for human rights violations', *Journal of Contemporary African Studies*, Vol 39, 2020, issue 1 pages 119-134.

⁴¹ A. Nnoko, Terrorism: A Dysfunctional Quagmire Over the Concept, *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 2, 44-52

⁴² The nexus between human trafficking and terrorism, www.un.org last accessed 10th March, 2024.

national functioning of public services and create widespread insurrection in the country.' Fighting terrorism is an indirect way of fighting child trafficking. Boko Haram and other terrorist organisations use child trafficking as a source of financing their activities. They equally forcibly recruit children as child soldiers and others for exploitation.

5. Conclusion & Recommendations

Child trafficking in conflict is a crime which has raised several concerns at the international, regional and national levels. As a member of the United Nations, Cameroon has made commendable legal strides in combatting child trafficking through the ratification and enactment of several human rights/anti-trafficking treaties. However, significant reforms are required to align its legal framework with international best practices. It is on this premise that the study recommends that;

There is need for a standardised legal definition of a 'child' in international law. The Convention on the Rights of the Child explicitly says a child is a person below the age of 18. Cameroon should ensure this legal definition is made uniform across its national laws.

It proposes that the marriageable age of girls in Cameroon be raised to 18 years to comply with the CRC, Maputo Protocol and the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of a Child. This will reduce the number of children whose parents often force them into early marriages.

It is recommended that, to fully understand the phenomenon of TIP, particularly child trafficking, the term 'exploitation of persons' as referenced in the UN Palermo Protocol needs to be clearly defined. While the protocol provides examples of the acts that could be considered exploitation, it does not explicitly define what exploitation means, leaving room for various conceptualisations of the term.

The 2011 anti-trafficking law should be amended to criminalise the recruitment of children into armed groups, use of children in terrorism, organ harvesting, and ritual killings. There is equally the need to establish separate penalties for child trafficking since it is distinct from adult trafficking.

It is equally important for the state to create specialized victim support units for trafficked children. Children need specific protection and unlike adults they have peculiar rehabilitation needs. The law should include provisions for safe houses and rehabilitation programs for child survivors.

Cameroon should ratify the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court which gives backing to the Palermo Protocol in order to strengthen international cooperation on

anti-trafficking efforts. After this ratification Cameroon will be able to make prosecutions for trafficking as a war crime.

The paper also recommends that international legal frameworks can only be effective if there are supervisory or monitoring bodies to ensure that states fulfill their anti-trafficking obligations. It is not enough for laws to exist; the implementation of these laws truly matters.

The study recommends anti-trafficking laws be well publicized through increased collaboration with civil society organisations.

6. References

- Ashukem, J., 'To give a dog a bad name to kill It-Cameroon's anti-terrorism law as a strategic framework for human rights violations', *Journal of Contemporary African Studies*, Vol 39, 2020, issue 1 pages 119-134.
- Dempsey, M., et al, 'Defining Sex Trafficking in International and Domestic Law: Mind the Gaps', *Emory International Law Review*, 2012, Vol 26 pp 136-162.
- Eyumeneh, N., 'What does the future hold for our Children? Child Trafficking in Cameroon and India', Published Master's Thesis, Central European University, Department of Human Rights, 2015 p 42
- Eyumeneh, N., 'Breast Ironing, a Silent Case of Violence Against Girls in Cameroon', *Republica y Derecho*, 2023 pp. 1-67
- Hughues, P., Child's Right Protection in Cameroon, *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, ISSN NO: 2769-996X 2024 P. 5
- Kam, H., 'Child Trafficking Across the Cameroon/Nigeria Border: A Historical Perspective', *Covenant University Journal of Politics and International Affairs*, Vol. 4 No. 1, pg 1-16, pp 1 2016
- Muraszkiewicz, J., et al, Human Trafficking in Conflict: Context, Causes and the Military, Crime Prevention and Security Management, *International Journal of Refugee Law*, Vol 33, Issue 2, 2021 pp.368-371
- Mbella, N., Human Rights Implications of Child Trafficking in Conflict Situations: Case Study of the Conflict in the English-Speaking Region of Cameroon, *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, ISSN NO: 2770-0003, 2021 pp 60-64
- Mower G. A., The Convention on the Rights of the Child: International Law Support for Children, 1997, pp. vii, 28 and 41-42. 89

- Nagavveni, L., 'International and Non-International Armed Conflicts and Application of International Humanitarian Law as *Lex Specialis*', *Chotangpur Law Journal*, Vol 11, No. 11, 2017, p.78-91
- Nji, L., 'The Enforceability of International Convention Against Child labour in Cameroon: Implications for Human Security in the Armed Conflicts in the North West and South West Regions, Published Ph.D Thesis in Comparative Politics, University of Buea, 2021
- Nnoko, A., 'Terrorism: A Dysfunctional Quagmire Over the Concept, *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 2, 44-52
- Sands, M., UDHR and Modern Slavery: Exploring the Challenges of Fulfilling the Universal Promise to End Slavery in All its Forms, *The Political Quarterly*
- Sloth–Nielsen, J., 'A Dutiful Child: The Implications of Article 31 of the African Children's Charter', *Journal of African Law* 2008, Vol 52, No 2, 159-189, 159
- Titanji, B., 'Curbing the Tides of Human Trafficking and Slavery', Design Publishers, Limbe Cameroon, 2019.
- Vijayarasa, R., A move in the Right Direction? The Model Law against Trafficking in Persons and the ILO Operational Indicators, *International Migration* 2018, Vol.57 Issue 1, 177-191
- A Significant Step Forward: CEDAW Committee adopts new General Recommendation on Trafficking in Women and Girls, www.equalitynow.org last accessed 10th March, 2024.
- African Charter on Human and People's Rights, available at www.achpr.org last accessed 10th March, 2024.
- Cameroon Penal Code, <https://www.justiceandpeacebamenda.org> last accessed 24th April, 2024
- Cameroon, <https://www.ijrcenter.org/country-factsheets> last accessed 10th March, 2024.
- CEDAW Emphasises its Concern Over Trafficking in Women and Girls, available at www.opiniojuris last accessed 10th March, 2024.
- General recommendation No. 38 (2020) on trafficking in women and girls in the context of global migration, available at www.reliefweb.int last accessed 10th March, 2024.

Global Initiative Against Transnational Organised Crime, Connecting Human Trafficking and Conflict, available at globalinitiative.net last accessed 15th July, 2024.